

**Western Fallacies and the “Monkeyism” Theory:
A Philosophical Enquiry into why some Men are not Humans**

Cyrille Ngamen Kouassi, (PhD)

Department of Philosophy and Religious Studies,
College of Humanities,
Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State
Cyrillengamen@sau.edu.ng

Nwachukwu, Chituru Udo, (PhD)

Department of History and International Studies
Babcock University,
Ilishan-Remo Ogun State,
nwachukwuc@babcock.edu.ng

And

Akinsanya Atchrimi Adebayo

Department of Languages (French Unit),
Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State
E-mail: aakinsanya@sau.edu.ng

Received: 12-06-2023

Accepted: 05-10-2023

Published: 31-12-2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10547315>

Abstract

The "Western Fallacies and the 'Monkeyism' Theory" explores the historical impact of Western colonialism on African identity and culture. It aims to debunk the fallacious theory that labeled Africans as primitive, uncultured, and inferior through the metaphor of "monkeyism." The author analyzes the tactics used by Westerners to enforce these beliefs, including changing African names, dismissing traditional religions, discrediting medicine, and imposing Western dress codes and manners. The papers further presents a counterargument, termed the "Demonkeyism" answer, to invalidate the degrading theory. It emphasizes the richness and validity of African cultures, traditions, and various aspects of life, asserting that they are in line with the journey toward real development. The author advocates for a paradigm shift in the perception of African cultures and traditions, stressing the need for Africans to assert their own identity without relying on Western validation. The paper calls for a departure from the blame game mentality, urging present-day Africans to decolonize their mindset, innovate according to their strengths, and embrace a neo-African

personality for genuine development. The author acknowledges the role of talking and drawing attention as a starting point in the pursuit of progress and development for Africa.

Keywords: “Western fallacies, “monkeyism” theory, African personality, liberation, fallacy

Introduction

If this paper sounds either polemical or argumentative in part, I can only hope that it will be understood from the point of view of a quest for African personality, liberation and development. Basically, a fallacy is an error in reasoning that tends to be psychologically persuasive. (Ngamen, 2014). Philosophy being the love of wisdom has as one of its major assignments through logic, the duty to unmask or invalidate some of the fallacies that are inimical to the progress, well-being and development of mankind irrespective of the skin colour or location whence the title of this lecture: “Western fallacies and the “monkeyism” theory: A philosophical enquiry into why some men are not humans.”

This lecture, therefore, is an attempt to debunk the “time yellowed” impression of some people especially the Western world that Africans are lazy, primitive, uncultured and good for nothing whence the “monkeyism” theory. Africans, such people would contend must be “civilized”,

“cultured” and exposed to “real development”. From the positions of the above school of thought the following questions appear very necessary and unavoidable: Who is a human being and how does he / she look like? If all men are equal before God then why and how is it that some men are not humans? Is there any relationship between culture and race? Does the qualification for being a human being dependent on the whims and caprices of other fellowmen?

Should a culture be “superior?” or “inferior” to the other? If yes, why and how? Is culture hereditary? If no, then what is the way forward for present day Africa?

Reactions to the above questions will help the author of this work address the complex notions of western fallacies and the “monkeyism” theory as far as the African continent is concerned. In the first instance, I will analyse and expose the major machineries or tactics put in place by the West in order to keep and convince Africans that they are and should remain monkey-like. It is an opportunity to understand why and how Eurocentric historians managed to convince the world to believe that Africa had no history and therefore Africans could not be considered as “real human beings.”

The second part of this lecture is what I call the “Demonkeyism” answer. This is where I will attempt to demonstrate and invalidate the fallacious theory of “monkeyism”. In other words, it is an opportunity for me to prove that actually, African cultures

and traditions, Arts and Aesthetics, Education, Politics, Economy, Religion,

Ethics and Morality were and are still very sound and in line with the journey towards real development. In that case therefore, they have nothing to do with the issues of superiority or inferiority when it comes to the relationship with the West. Since all men are “humans” and equal before God therefore, Africa should not be an exception.

The third and last part of this lecture is a projection towards a neo-African personality and development as a way forward. It is an opportunity for us to understand that having established the fallacious nature of the “monkeyism” theory and also based on the findings that all men are “humans” and equal irrespective of their skin colour, origin and location; So in the search for the way forward, the twenty first century Africa needs a paradigm shift, a kind of “Copernican revolution” in the ways and manners she presently perceives and expresses her cultures and traditions. In other words, as far as development is concerned, each culture has its own peculiarity and conditioning therefore, it is high time for present day Africans to understand that they do not need “others” especially the West to name, define and even classify them.

WESTERN FALLACIES AND THE MONKEYISM” THEORY

Basically, Colonialism is best understood as the political and economic dependence of one people on another. (Ngamen, 2016a), it is very shocking to realize that even till date, after many decades of the so-called independence of the African continent, most Africans still rely on the “other” that is, the Western world to name, qualify, define and even classify them.

It is on record that Westerners came to Africa with the mandate to completely annex the mentality and concepts of the black people. In their own opinion, African people were of different race and culture. They were ugly and primitive (Ngamen, 2010: 192). Therefore, it was necessary for Westerners to expose black men to progress, development and to the light of civilization because to them, progress, development and civilization were their exclusive rights.

White men alleged that the black man intelligence quotient was low, his vocabulary had no abstract nouns, he was incapable of abstract thinking, he had no philosophy, he did not understand natural phenomena, he has no idea of causality. His mind was full of magical notions. (Ngamen, 2016: 11-16) Throughout the ages, evidences have been build up to show that the cultures of African peoples are inferior to those of the Whites and this must be so because Africans belong to an inferior race or species. No wonder General Norton de Matos, former Governor of Portuguese territory of Angola in 1953 had this to say about his mission in Africa:

In Africa our objectives has been to convert the blacks, to lift them from the moral and material misery they were in when we encountered them, to clothe tem, to give them human habitation, to make them rural proprietors, or to transform them into artisans. (Ngamen, 2016a: 14).

Moreso, Eurocentric historians have made the world to believe that Africa had no history (Adegbulu, 2011:17182). According to Trevor Roper, pre-colonial African continent is a little more than “the unrewarding gyrations of barbarous tribes in picturesque but irrelevant corners of the

globe” (1966:a). And for Arnold Toynbee, one of the renowned British historians to conclude as follows: “when we classify mankind by colour the only one of the primary races. ... which has not made a creative contribution to any of our twenty one civilizations is the black race.

(1934:180)

From the forgoing, it is evident that white men refused to study and understand the Blacks, instead they categorically and blindly condemned everything black. One of the lines that the conquerors/white men drew is that between reason and unreason (Mogobe, 2003). White men borrowed Aristotle’s definition of man to justify their evil mission in Africa.

Aristotle, one of the major figures in ancient Western philosophy is credited with the definition of man as “a rational animal”. This implies that any animal whose being or nature includes reason as his/her distinctive characteristic is a “real” human being or a man. Besides, any other animal which might look like a “real” human being but without reason does not qualify as a human being. Rather it is simply an animal with unreason or a monkey! In white men understanding and interpretation of Aristotle’s definition of man, black men were animals with unreason. So the line between reason and unreason was drawn to differentiate between white and black. White men became animals with reason while black men remained animals with unreason or monkey-like. This line indicated not only the boundary between reason and unreason but it also assigned competences, rights and obligations in agreement with reason and unreason respectively. In this way, it also established the nature of the relationship between those inside the line of reason.

It is on record that the right to freedom and competence to exercise one’s will became the exclusive right of rational animals that is, white men. In their relationship with one another, rational animals or white men had the obligation to recognize, respect and protect the right to freedom and freedom of the will.

However, it was out of place for animals with unreason that is, black men to claim the competences or the right that did not belong to them by nature. Therefore, in their relationship with reasonable animals, the animals with unreason that is, black people were disallowed in advance to demand obligation that befit only rational animals/white men. According to the whites, Aristotle’s definition of man as a “rational animal” excluded the Africans. In essence, this philosophy denied humanity to all animals with unreason. By definition, such animals-black men included could not and did not qualify to be humans in the genuine sense of the word. Therefore, the black man was to be treated only as an animal because by nature he was an animal with unreason. Accordingly, it was necessary and proper to conquer and enslave the black man. The conquerors/ white men saw no distinction between the Cartesian Cogito and their so-called God given mission in Africa. In other words, “I think, therefore, I conquer and enslave “became the practical application by the conquerors white men of Rene Descartes “I think, therefore, I exist.” (1998:160).

From their interpretation of Aristotle’s definition of man to justify their conquest, white men also took particular interest in African traditional religion, music, medicine and African proper names. White men dismissed all African indigenous belief as heathen. In their attempt to impose their

culture on Africans, white men succeeded in dividing parents from children, villages from villages, tribes from tribes and to a large extent, countries from countries (Ngamen, 2012:44). White men wanted to make sure that all evidence of African culture was gradually suppressed or eradicated from living memory. This is evidenced in African proper names, church music, medicine, dress codes and manners just to mention but a few.

African Proper Names

In line with their mission to dominate and colonize the blacks, European missionaries purposely Anglicized African proper names in order to indicate that the bearers had become Christians and therefore “civilized” or “cultured.” In his book titled *Africa Unbound* (1963), Alex Quaison-Sackey gives an account of what actually happened in Ghana. According to him, when European missionaries arrived Ghana they changed “Seki” to “Sackey,” “Obu” became “Rocson,” “Kunti” became

“Blackson” and “Dadzie” became “steel Dadzie” to mention but a few. There is no doubt that apart from Ghana many other African countries witnessed the same scenario/ tragedy. We are also told that among the Ibibio in Nigeria, for someone to prove that he/she was truly converted from his / her pagan ways to Christianity, his/her attire, personal comportment, his/her household articles, his/her house or place of abode, all had to approximate the European style as closely as possible. Their native names were either discarded or anglicised. For instance, “Akabom” became

“Cobhan,” “Efiom” became “Ephraim,” “Orok became “Duke,” “Antigha” became “Antera,” “Abasi” became

“Bassey,” “Ansa” became “Henshaw” and so on. (UDO, 2002:21).

It is unfortunate that black men unwillingly saw their names and their own individuality being obliterated with a quality that was distinctly not African. (Ngamen, 2012)

African Traditional Religions

From name changing white men also criticized and discarded African Traditional Religions. Playing drums in African churches for instance, was sacrilegious and heathen. In fact black men were infidels and knew nothing about the true “God” that is, the God of Jesus Christ. Black men did not know God because through their irrationality or unreason they believed in the mythic gods. According to white men, the gods of blackmen were at best the highest form of aesthetic expression and, at worst were objects of superstition. They had to be abandoned. This was strengthened by the claim that God had now revealed himself through Jesus Christ. Since this provided certainty about the being and the destiny of humanity, it was no longer necessary to have faith in the so-called mythic gods of Africa. The conviction here was that the God of Jesus

Christ was the one and only true God and this justified the “burial” or discardment of all other so-called lesser gods in Africa. Blackmen, being animals with unreason lacked the ability to know the true God and therefore, had no religion in white man’s sense of the word. Consequently, African believers were again deprived of the well springs of their own culture and identity.

African Medicine

White men had no doubt in their mind that the so-called African medicine was inferior, primitive, savage and valueless. It is on record that any African Christian under the dictate of European missionaries was expected to seek help from the Doctor at the hospital and not from the

African Herbalist. (Ngamen, 2012). It is unfortunate that white men purposely ignored the African distinction between an herbalist and a trickster or jujuman. White men called all of them “witch doctors” or “medicine men”.

African Dress Code and Manners

As animals with unreason, black men knew nothing about good or bad manners. In fact, wearing European clothes, eating with knife and fork was a mark of civilization and development. Every black man was expected and is still expected to say “Sir” to a white man. Even romance between a white man and black woman and vice – versa was sacrilegious. (Ngamen, 2012). It is striking to observe that the educated Africans mostly in the French and Portuguese speaking territories, ceased to be regarded as Africans. They became French or Portuguese.

In line with the above, along with what is going on in present day Africa, it is obvious that psychologically, politically and socio- culturally, the colonizer/white man has succeeded in convincing the colonized that is, the black man, that he/she is lazy, good for nothing, unintelligent, wicked, inferior, backward or underdeveloped. That he/she lacks personality and he/she is not checked by any inhibition of civilization (Ngamen, 2012) So, constantly and forcefully confronted with this image of him, set forth and imposed on all institutions and in every human contact, the black man ends up recognizing it as one would a detested nick name which has become a familiar description.

Unfortunately, this willful creation and spread of this mythical and degrading portrait of the colonized / black man by the colonizer ends up by being accepted and lived by the black man. It thus acquires a certain amount of reality and contributes to the true portrait of the black man. This constitutes one of the most serious blows suffered by the black man in present day Africa because he is being separated from his original culture and history.

According to Memi (1965), we have no idea of what the colonized would have been without colonization but we certainly see what has happened as a result of it. To subdue and exploit, the colonizer pushed the colonized out of his historical and social cultural current. Today what is real and verifiable is that the black man’s culture, society and technology are seriously adulterated if not completely damaged. Again, what is pathetic is that even in this twenty first century the standing order seems to remain that is, the black man must resemble the white man. Almost everything in the black man is out of style, inefficient and derisory. The fellow black man has ceased to be one of his people at heart. He is now ashamed of what is most real in him, of the only

thing not borrowed that is, his identity. (Ngamen, 2012). All these simply because of western fallacies and their monkeyism theory.

CONCLUSION

Throughout this lecture I have attempted to show how it is very shocking to realize that even till date, after many decades of the so-called independence of the African

Continent, most Africans still rely on the “Other” that is, the Western world to name, qualify, define and even classify them.

This is simply because during the period of colonization and imperialism, Eurocentric historians and missionaries managed to convince the world to believe that not only Africa had no history, more so, her inhabitants were primitive, irrational, uncultured and good for nothing whence, the “monkeyism” theory. Fortunately for Africa, with the help of modern anthropologists, sociologists and archaeologists alike, along with more sophisticated empirical methods of research, it has now become a fact that all the technical and scientific theories, all the analyses of cultures and races, all the attempts to establish the innate inferiority of the black man are vain efforts and there-after, fallacious. In other words, the good news is that despite all efforts to prove that the black man belonged to a lower species than the white, it was too much of a man to be an ape.

There is a common humanity all over the world, or to paraphrase an Akan proverb from Ghana: in human flesh there is no edge of cultivation- no boundary. This simply means that all human flesh is of one kind, all mankind is one species. Consequently, each culture has its own peculiarity and conditioning. It is not a question between the two races of inferiority or superiority, or reason and unreason. There is no absolute or essential superiority on the one side. It is a question of difference of endowment and difference of destiny.

It is obvious that no amount of training or culture will make the Negro a European, on the other hand, no lack of training or deficiency of culture will make the European a Negro. The Negro and the European races do not move in the same groove, on the contrary, they move on parallel lines with limitless distance between them. That is why as far as progress and development are concerned, Negro and European races will never meet in the line of their activities. To paraphrase Blyden (1967) black and white are not identical as some think, but unequal, they are distinct but equal.

Now, according to a Chinese proverb: when you blame others you are nowhere, when you blame yourself you have done half journey and when you blame nobody then you have arrived.

In line with the fore going, I humbly submit that it is high time for present day Africans to go beyond the blame game attitude because Africa is not the only continent that has been colonized. The Koreans, Vietnamese, Chinese, French to mention just a few, were also colonized, but look at

UT UNIVERSITY PRESS

where they are today in term of genuine development! Why should our own case be different? Africa must wake up. The above mentioned countries dreamt and woke up to realize their dreams. It is high time for Africa to follow suit. We must re-decolonize our current mentality, invent and innovate according to our specific areas of specialization and strength because there lies the hope of Africa.

Yes, I anticipate that I will be accused of only talking and drawing attention, but as a matter of fact, some people have to talk and draw attention, some to hear or listen while some are to do or practicalize and some to reap the fruits of the action. We just have to genuinely start from somewhere may be by beginning to pay serious attention to African philosophers. Progress and development are inter-generational and Africa cannot and should not be an exception.

REFERENCES

- Adegbulu, F. (2011). "Pre-colonial West African diplomacy: Its nature and impact" *The Journal of International Social Research* 4/18
- Andah, B. (1998). *African Anthropology* C. I. Ltd. Ibadan
- Aristotle, (1962). *Politics*. England: Penguin Books
- Barth, H. (2011). *Travels and Discoveries in North and Central Africa: Being a Journal of an expedition undertaken under the Auspices of H. B. M's Government, in the.....collection-African Studies*.(Vol.4) Cambridge University Press.
- Blyden W. E (1967). *Christianity, Islam and the Negro Race* Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh pp262-283
- Busia, K. A (1962). *The Challenge of Africa*. London the Pall Mall Press, 97-106.
- Diop, A. C (1974). *The African Origin of Civilization: Myth or Reality* Lawrence Hill Books Chicago Review Press. Chicago.
- Descartes, R (1998). *Discourse on Method and the Meditations*. Penguin Classics.
- Eboh, B. O. (1980). *Philosophy in the Growth of Nigeria* - Ikot Ekpene
- Ekei, J. (2004). "Governance in Traditional Africa: Implications for a Nascent Modern African Policy" in J. Obi Oguejuofor (Ed) *Philosophy, Democracy and Responsible Governance in Africa* (Enugu: Delta Publication).
- Evans, S. M. (2001). *Black and White in the Southern States: A study of the race problem in the United States from a 75 South African Point of 76 view*. University of South Carolina Press.
- Gyekye, K. (1987). *An Essay on African Philosophical Thought the Akan Conceptual Scheme* (Cambridge University Press).
- Gyekye, k. (1993). *Person and Community*. (Cambridge University Press).
- Hayford, C. (1911). *Ethiopia Unbound: Studies in Race Emancipation*. (Cambridge University Press).

- Hountondji, P. (1981). “*Que Peut la Philosophie?*” in Diemer (ed) *Philosophy in the Present Situation of Africa*. Franz- Steeiner.
- Kaphagawani, DN. (1993). “Democratic Practice in Africa: Some Arguments” in *Quest* Vol. III, No 2. December
- Kenyatha, J. (1953). *Facing Mount Kenya*. Marhins Seeker & Warbung Ltd. (Mercury Books) London.
- Kidd, D. (1925). *The Essential Kafir*. New York: The Macmillan Company.
- Kwegyir Aggrey, J. (1920). “Black and White keys”. Speech delivered during a missionary visit in South Africa. Wikipedia.
- Lieris, M. (2020). *Phantom Africa*, Transl. By Brent Hayes Edwards. (Seagull Books London Ltd).
- Levi – Strauss, C. (1952). *Race and History*, UNESCO, Press, FRANCE.
- Masefield, J (1903). *Laugh and Be Merry* Internet Poems. com.
- Molema, S. M. (1969). *The Bantu: Past and Present*. Frank Cass & Co. Ltd. London.
- Memi, A. (1965). *The Colonizer and the Colonized*. New York: Orion Press.
- Mogobe, B.R. (2003). “African Democratic Tradition: Oneness, Consensus and Openness: A Reply to Wamba- dia. Wamba” in *Quest* Vol VI, No. 2, December.
- Mogobe, B.R. (2003). “Justice and Restitution in African Political Thought” in *The African Philosophy Reader* P. H. Coetzee and AP. J. Roux (eds) New York: Routledge.
- Mphahlele E. (1974). *The African Image* (London: Faber & Faber).
- Ngamen, K. C. (2014). *Fundamentals of Philosophy, Logic and Human Existence* NelPhil. Ibadan. 216p.
- Metuonu, I. C. (2016a). “Is there such thing as African Culture in the 21st century? A Philosophical Analysis” *Journal of Philosophy, Culture, and Religion*, Vol. 15, 11 – 16 USA.
- Ngamen K. C. (2016b). “Modern Nigeria and the roots of Corruption: A historico – philosophical Reflection” *Journal of Philosophy, Culture, and Religion*, Vol. 17, USA 6 - 11.
- Ngamen K. C. (2016c). “The State, Nationhood, Ethno- politics and Democracy in Modern Africa: A Philosophical Reflection”. *Journal of Philosophy, Culture and Religion*, Vol 17 USA, 12 – 17.
- Ngamen K. C. (2016d). “Just War Theory and the Question of Terrorism in Modern Africa: which way forward? *Journal of Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol. No 1 USA. 45 – 51.
- Ngamen K. C. (2010). “Multiculture and the question of African Unity: the way forward” *International Journal of Politics and Development in Africa*_No 1. Vol. 2 Ondo State, Nigeria, 190 – 199.
- Ngamen K. C. (2012). “Cultural practices and development in Modern Africa: Lessons for the 21st Century” *Nigerian Journal of Policy and Development* Continental Books Project, Ltd. Abuja. Vol 7 & 8, 44 – 52.

- Ngamen K. C. (2018). "On Plato's Political Philosophy" in Izibili, M. A. Isanbor, P. O. and Attah, S. U. (eds). *Studies in Philosophy and society: A book of Readings* Vol I. Kagoma Dpt. of Philosophy, Albertine Institute Jos. 246 – 261
- Ngamen K. C. (2015). "Globalization, African Cultures and Development: Philosophical Appraisal of lessons for the 21st century" in *dilemma of the bat: African and Globalization in a Changing World* gold line and Jacobs Publishing New Jersey. USA 34-44
- Ngamen, K. C. (2009). *Introduction to Logic and Critical Thinking*. National Open University of Nigeria (URL: www.noun.edu.ng)
- Ngamen, K. C. (2008). *Nigerian Peoples and Culture*. National Open University of Nigeria (URL: www.noun.edu.ng)
- Ngamen, K. C. (2020). "On Patriotism, Democracy Ethnicity and The Question of Development in Modern Africa: A Philosophical Reflection" (Unpublished)
- Ngamen, K. C. (2020). "Philosophy, Good Governance and Development in Modern Africa: The Nigerian Predicament" (Unpublished)
- Nkrumah, K. (1961). *I speak of freedom*, Panet books Ltd. London. 125-34
- Offor, F. (2011). "Democracy as an issue in African philosophy" in *Core Issues African Philosophy*, Olusegun Oladipo (ed) Hope Publication Ltd. Ibadan
- Oguejiofor, O. J. (2000). *Philosophy and the African Predicament*. Hope Publications Ltd Ibadan
- Okolo, C. B. (1992). *Philosophy: Introductory Questions*. Ibadan
- Oladipo, O. (1992). *The Idea of African Philosophy*: Molecular Publishers, Ibadan
- Oluwole, S. B. (2004). "Democracy and Indigenous Governance: The Nigerian Experience" in J. Obi Oguejiofor (ed) *Philosophy, Democracy and Responsible Governance in Africa* (Enugu) Delta Publication.
- Omeregbe, J. (1990). *Knowing Philosophy* JoJa, Lagos Plato (1995). *The Republic*, Harmonds worth: Penguins.
- Przeworski, A. (1988). "Democracy as a contingent outcome of Conflicts" in John Elster and Rune Slagstad (eds) *Constitutionalism and Democracy* (Cambridge University Press)
- Quaison – Sackey, A. (1963). *Africa Unbound*, London: Andre Deutsh Ltd.
- Shakespeare, W. (1597). *Love's Labour's Lost*, Minnesota University Press.
- Toynbee, A. J. (1934). *A Study of History*. Oxford University Press.
- Trevor- Roper (1966). *The Rise of Christian Europe* (London: Thames & Hudson)
- Udo, E. (2002). *Religion and Cultural Identity*. Hope Publications, Ibadan
- Wiredu. K. (1980). *Philosophy and an African Culture*. (Cambridge University Press).